

Polarographic Behaviour of Nickel and Zinc Complexes with Pyrrolidinone-2

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Polarographic reduction of nickel and zinc in pyrrolidinone-2 gives a single, well-defined wave at d.m.e. In both the cases the wave has been found to be diffusion-controlled and irreversible. Koutecky's treatment as extended by Meites and Israel has been applied to calculate kinetic parameters. The decrease in charge transfer coefficient (αn) and electrode reaction rate constant ($k^{\circ}_{r,n}$) at increasing concentration of pyrrolidinone-2 indicates that the reduction process in both the systems switches over to more irreversible side. Conditions have been developed for the quantitative determination of these metals.

MARK and Reilley¹ investigated the behaviour of nickel ion in pyridine and the polarographic behaviour of nickel in 2-aminopyridine², citrulline³, 4-hydroxyhydroline⁴, tryptophan⁴ and pyrozo⁵ has been studied by many workers. The discharge of zinc at d.m.e. has been studied in the presence of different complexing agents such as pyridine and 3-methyl pyridine⁶, 1,3-propanediamine⁷, ethylenediamine⁸, propylene⁹, monoethanolamine¹ and iminodiacetic acid¹¹.

Pyrrolidinone-2¹²⁻¹³ has been used in the extraction of hydrocarbons. Pyrrolidinone has also been determined polarographically in waste and natural water by Zhantalai and Sergeeva¹⁴. However the polarographic study of nickel and zinc with pyrrolidinone-2 has not been taken up so far. The present study deals with the polarography of Zn(II) and Ni(II) with pyrrolidinone-2.

Experimental

Solutions of Ni(II) and Zn(II) were prepared from Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O and ZnSO₄·7H₂O (A.R.) in double distilled water. Pyrrolidinone-2 was of Fluka, G.R. grade. KNO₃ solution was used to keep the ionic strength constant at 0.1 M.

A manual Toshniwal polarograph in conjunction with polyflex galvanometer was used. All measurements were made at 30±0.1°. Purified nitrogen gas was passed through the solutions to remove the dissolved oxygen. Saturated calomel electrode (SCE) was used as a reference electrode. The dropping mercury electrode (d.m.e.) had the following characteristics (in 0.1 M KNO₃; open circuit); $m=2.90$ mg/sec, $t=2.9$ sec, $m^{2/3} t^{1/6}=2.43$ mg^{2/3} sec^{-1/6}, $h_{corr}=58.7$ cm. Triton X-100 (0.005%) was used as maximum suppressor.

The number of electrons, n , involved in the reduction process was determined by millicoulometric method of DeVries and Kroon¹⁵, using

d.m.e. as cathode and the mercury pool as anode. The formula used was

$$n_2 = n_1 \left(\frac{\Delta i_a \text{ cad}}{i_a \text{ cad}} \right) \left(\frac{i_a \text{ sub}}{\Delta i_a \text{ sub}} \right) \frac{V_1 C_1}{V_2 C_2}$$

where $i_a \text{ cad}$ is the original diffusion current (corrected for the residual current) for cadmium solution, V_1 the volume, C_1 the concentration of cadmium solution, and $\Delta i_a \text{ cad}$ is the charge in diffusion current produced by the electrolysis; $i_a \text{ sub}$, V_2 and C_2 are the corresponding quantities for the solution of the substance; n_1 and n_2 are the number of electrons involved in the reduction of cadmium and substance at d.m.e., respectively. As the concentration and volume in respect of cadmium and substance were the same ($V_1=V_2=0.3$ ml; $C_1=C_2=1 \times 10^{-3} M$), the last factor in the above equation is unity. In the present systems n was found to be 2.

Results and Discussion

Polarograms of solutions containing $1 \times 10^{-2} M$ Zn(II) or Ni(II) and 0.1M pyrrolidinone-2 were taken at different pH. It was observed that the negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ was maximum at pH 6 in both the cases. On further increasing the pH, metals got precipitated. Hence pH 6 was chosen for studying the complex formation. The concentration of the ligand was varied from 0.1 to 0.6M. In each case a single well defined diffusion-controlled wave appeared. The plots of i_d vs $\sqrt{h_{corr}}$ were found to be linear and passing through the origin, thereby showing the diffusion-controlled nature of the reduction. With increase in pyrrolidinone-2, the $E_{1/2}$ shifted towards more negative potential showing complex formation between metal ions and ligand.

The conventional log plots of the reduction waves for Zn(II) and Ni(II) in pyrrolidinone-2 were

linear and their slope values indicated the irreversible nature of the waves for both the systems. Hence, Koutecky's theoretical treatment as extended by Meites and Israel¹⁶ was applied to determine the values of transfer coefficient (αn) and forward electrode rate constant ($k_{f,h}^0$).

A perusal of the data in Tables 1 and 2 shows a decrease in charge transfer coefficient with an increase in concentration of pyrrolidinone-2. $k_{f,h}^0$ also decreases with increasing concentration of pyrrolidinone-2, indicating the tendency of the wave to move towards irreversibility.

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC DATA FOR NICKEL-PYRROLIDINONE-2 SYSTEM

Ni(II) = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$; $\mu = 0.1 M KNO_3$; pH = 6; n = 2

[Pyrrolidinone] (M)	i_d (μA)	$-E_{1/2}$ vs SCE (V)	Slope (mV)	$D^{1/2} \times 10^3$ (cm ² /sec)	αn	$k_{f,h}^0$ (cm/sec)
0.1	9.01	1.008	124	2.68	0.473	2.48×10^{-9}
0.2	8.58	1.060	180	2.50	0.417	1.84×10^{-9}
0.3	8.37	1.105	180	2.44	0.417	8.64×10^{-10}
0.4	8.29	1.192	186	2.42	0.399	3.91×10^{-10}
0.5	8.01	1.228	140	2.38	0.389	3.55×10^{-10}
0.6	8.01	1.280	146	2.33	0.371	3.09×10^{-10}

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC DATA FOR ZINC-PYRROLIDINONE-2 SYSTEM

Zn(II) = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$; $\mu = 0.1 M KNO_3$; pH = 6; n = 2

[Pyrrolidinone] (M)	i_d (μA)	$-E_{1/2}$ vs SCE (V)	Slope (mV)	$D^{1/2} \times 10^3$ (cm ² /sec)	αn	$k_{f,h}^0$ (cm/sec)
0.1	14.3	1.108	79	4.17	0.686	1.57×10^{-13}
0.2	14.01	1.160	82	4.08	0.661	9.59×10^{-14}
0.3	13.87	1.208	84	4.04	0.645	5.04×10^{-14}
0.4	13.87	1.260	87	4.04	0.623	3.27×10^{-14}
0.5	13.44	1.322	92	3.92	0.589	2.95×10^{-14}
0.6	13.16	1.345	94	3.84	0.577	2.86×10^{-14}

Effect of metal ion concentration :

Polarograms over the concentration range of Zn = 1.00–3.50 mM and Ni = 1.01–3.00 mM were drawn under the above mentioned conditions and the diffusion currents were measured by the extrapolation method. The values of diffusion current constant (I) was calculated using Ilkovic equation $I = i_d / cm^{2/3} / t^{1/6}$ [Zn(II) = 5.88 and Ni(II) = 3.71] which were constant over the metal ion concentration range mentioned above. The polarographic results are therefore used for the quantitative determination of these metals.

General procedure for the determination of Zn(II) and Ni(II) :

A calibration curve for each of the metals was prepared by recording the polarograms of the metal at various concentrations in 0.1M pyrrolidinone-2 solution at pH 6. The i_d values of the polarograms were plotted against concentration of the metal ions

and polarogram of solution containing the metal in unknown concentration was recorded under identical conditions. The i_d values of this wave were referred to the calibration curve and concentration of the metal (Table 3) in the solution of alloy thus determined.

Effect of diverse ions :

0.1 mg salt of different cations were added separately to aliquots containing 1.6085 mg nickel or 3.0468 mg zinc. Co(II) and Te(IV) interfered in the determination of both and Zn(II) and Ni(II) also interfered in the determination of each other. In both the cases all the added ions had no effect on estimation (Table 4).

TABLE 3—POLAROGRAPHIC DETERMINATION OF METALS IN ALLOY

Alloy	Certified composition	Amount of metal (mg)		Error %
		Taken	Found (average)*	
Brass No. 412	Cu : 58.18, Pb : 2.56, Zn : 38.99, Fe : 0.09, Sn : 0.12.	Zn : 1.472	Zn : 1.470	-0.136
	Monel 400	Ni : 68.0, C : 0.15, S : 0.0024, Mn : 0.01, Si : 0.5, Fe : 2.5, Cu : 31.0	Ni : 0.926	Ni : 0.924
Stainless Steel	Ni : 9.68, Cr : 18.0, Fe : 70.71.	Ni : 1.671	Ni : 1.669	-0.120
Inconel 600	Ni : 72.0, C : 0.15, Mn : 1.0, Fe : 8.0, S : 0.5, Cu : 0.50, Cr : 15.50	Ni : 2.202	Ni : 2.199	-0.136

* Average of five determinations.

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS

Amount of diverse ion taken = 1 mg

Ni : 1.6085 mg Zn : 3.0468 mg

Metal salt added	Amount of nickel found (mg)	Amount of zinc found (mg)
Aluminium nitrate	1.6077	3.0464
Antimony chloride	1.6075	3.0479
Bismuth nitrate	1.6085	3.0471
Cobalt nitrate	—	—
Copper chloride	1.6081	3.0452
Cadmium sulphate	1.6075	3.0458
Lead nitrate	1.6077	3.0468
Manganese acetate	1.6075	3.0469
Potassium telurite	—	—
Platinum chloride	1.6079	3.0473
Sodium tungstate	1.6088	3.0465
Uranyl acetate	1.6089	3.0473

Standard deviation Ni : 5.43×10^{-4} ; Zn : 7.86×10^{-4} .

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